

**INFORMATIONAL CONTRIBUTION OF SUSTAINABILITY
REPORTING IN MITIGATING AGENCY PROBLEM:
EVIDENCE FROM BANGLADESH**

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Abstract

The objective of the study is to examine whether sustainability disclosures are contributing to eliminating agency problem in Bangladeshi listed banking companies or not. The study covers all the listed commercial banks of the Dhaka stock exchange of Bangladesh for the year 2008-2019. Data regarding sustainable disclosures and other variables have been collected through the content analysis of the annual report. The association of sustainability disclosures and agency cost are investigated through multivariate regression analysis. Sustainability reporting has association with agency cost mitigation is the primary finding. The extent sustainability reporting has significant role in reducing agency problem. Furthermore, findings varied on the basis of the proxy used for measuring agency cost. Findings may have important implication in financial sectors of developing economy. The findings may be different for non-financial sector as well as non-listed company in different regulatory and socio-economic settings. There are a limited number of studies on agency problem in financial sectors. The study has used different proxy of agency cost as well as different measures of sustainability disclosures, which contribute to future studies in the relevant field.

Keywords: Agency problem, asymmetric information, sustainability reporting, corporate governance, earning management

1. Introduction

The actions of agents which are operated solely for their own interests at the expense of outside investors may lead to agency problem (Florackis & Ozkan, 2009). The key motives for the principal-agent problem are engagements of interests between two parties and the asymmetric information between them (as agents tend to possess more information than principals). Most companies in Bangladesh (BD) are primarily insider oriented, including substantial ownership of family (khan et al., 2013). Therefore, managements in most of the firms are literally just extensions of the dominant shareholders. Thus, the fundamental agency conflict among the firms can

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be termed as the conflict of insider and outsider owner. The majority shareholders control BOD and occupy managerial post, gain information on internal issues and use the information individual gain and deprive small investors. This high asymmetric information creates agency problems; gives insider owners the opportunity to pursue personal interest at the expense of small investors (Rashid, 2016). Literature asserted that conflict arises more because of weak governance, absence of effective monitoring, disciplining mechanism and information asymmetry among investors (principal) and managers (Agents) (Florackis & Ozkan, 2009). As corporate governance (internal monitoring mechanism) and external monitoring mechanism (creditors/banks) is significant for understanding and limiting the potential for suboptimal managerial action, a large number of studies were done on interaction between corporate governance (CG) characteristics such as ownership concentration, board of director arrangement, director ownership, executive compensation, audit quality and agency cost (Rashid, 2016; Ang et al., 2003; Khan et al., 2016).

A question might be raised whether corporate sustainability reporting (CSR) can also be effective to reduce agency cost as a monitoring mechanism, as investor suffers from asymmetric information that creates agency problem. Disclosures can reduce frictions of market of a company and the gap between internal and external resources costs through minimizing ununiformed information and agency costs (Shamsuddini & Golbaghi, 2017). Kim et al. (2012) used the Domini 400 Social Index and found that firms that are accountable to society appear lower income manipulation, as compared to non-responsible firms. Álvarez et al. (2008) pointed that disclosing more information regarding economic facts and long term managerial initiatives is a potential solution of mitigating agency problems. Thus additional disclosure is an effective monitoring mechanism for outsiders' shareholder. Akhtaruddin and Hossian (2008) affirm contribution of disclosures to efficiently handle potential conflicts between company's managers and stakeholders. Therefore, sustainability reporting is a monitoring mechanism to mitigate agency cost and, to protect shareholders interest.

Previous studies also revealed alternative findings also. Studies found that agency problem can influence managers to utilize corporate social responsibility (CSR) to hide their opportunistic behavior and corporate misconduct. Hahn and Kuhnen (2013) showed that managers involved in earning management, demonstrated improved representation of profitability and social responsibility activities to divert focus from financial irregularities. Therefore, more voluntary disclosures may leads poor quality financial and non-financial information, thus, resulting in less transparent information and wrong investment decision.

Present study investigates the relationship of agency problem with sustainability disclosures for listed commercial banks of Bangladesh, a highly regulated sector (Mazumder, 2024). Banks, as custodians of public trust, play a vital role in economic stability by transferring resources from surplus entities to deficit ones (Toader et al., 2018). Despite of accelerated expansion in banking sector and major contribution in monetization of rural economy, resource transfer from rural to urban areas, development of other businesses, banking is now most vulnerable business sector in Bangladesh (International Monetary Fund [IMF], 2019). Deficit in capital, inadequate credit information, poor governance, lengthy legal procedures, government interference in appointment of directors and political interference in

granting loan are making the problem more complex (Islam, 2019), which create trust issues to the investors and clients. Study on agency problems in Bangladeshi banking sectors is significant for three reasons. Firstly, in BD, banks face horizontal agency problem, because, different principals have diverse interest and goals. As a result, conflicts in listed banks in BD can be explained as a principal – principal agency conflict (Young et al., 2008; Rashid, 2016). Shapiro (2005) defined this type of agency problem as ‘Type 2’ agency problem between controlling shareholders and minority shareholders. Secondly, agency cost is the outcome of separation of ownership and different modes of financing all over the world may differ among countries because of different financial, political, legal and internal control mechanism (Rashid, 2015). While most of the studies focused on important internal and external monitoring mechanism for reducing agency cost in the context of developed countries, limited studies in emerging economy motivate to select Bangladesh. Finally, a lot of studies focused on this topic that surprisingly avoids or excludes financial institutions. But in real, banks have been more prone to earning management practices than non-financial organizations (Greenawalt & Sinkey, 1988). Their diversified financial operation and services (Lewis, 2009; Heilpern et al., 2009) are characterized by complexity and uncertainty (Mulbert, 2009), which essentially complicate their financial disclosure process (Hatherly & Kretschmar, 2011; Grougiou et al., 2014). Separate regulation for financial sector and different structures in financial statements make it difficult to consider the proxy of agency cost in banking sectors. Due to distinctive financial structure and income generating activities and existence of government regulation, the banking industry provides a unique scenario for agency cost (Mercado-Mendez & Willey, 1995). Moreover because of different financial structures and difficulty in developing proxies most of the studies on agency problems avoid banking sector to consider. (Rashid, 2015; Khan et al., 2016)

The study covers the data of all listed commercial banks of BD from 2008 to 2019. While section 2 provides literatures from prior studies and develops hypothesis, section 3 contains methodology including variables, model specification, sample selection and data collection. The result on the basis of regression analysis is presented in section 4, and in the end, section 5 draws conclusion highlighting limitations of the study and scope of future research.

2. Theoretical Underpinnings, Prior Research, and Hypotheses

2.1 Agency Problem and Contribution of Sustainability Reporting

Agency theory explains agency conflicts that may occur between principals and agents, such as company management and shareholders. These agency conflicts can threaten the company's performance (Syafriadi et al., 2023). Agency theory assumes agents (insider managers) opportunistic actions sometimes caused for owners/investors cost. According to agency theory developed by Jensen and Meckling in 1976, high asymmetric information can allow some stakeholders (especially insider managers) to take a disproportionate share of corporate profit; this may destroy firms' long term value. So agency cost arises from conflict of interest and information asymmetry. Managers take opportunity asymmetric information and utilize for their self-interest at the expense of principal interest (Walker, 1989), which

leads to moral hazard and adverse selection problems. Asquith and Mullins (1986) found that separation of management from shareholders empowered managers with superior information regarding company's financial condition and long term prospects. Their claim supported by Hill and Jones (1992) assumed that company managers are in a position to filter or distort the information that they disclose to stakeholders. Managers controlling over critical information complicate the agency problem.

Two important mechanisms are widely used to solve agency conflict hence reduce agency problems ; first one is to motivate managers to work at the best interest of organization in long run and the another is to provide relevant information to the stakeholders (Bushman & Smith, 2003). Corporate disclosure increases shareholders knowledge about firm management practices and better disclosure helps to reduce the cost of adverse selection and moral hazard. Thus, corporate disclosures intended at reducing information asymmetry in two ways: 1) disclosing sustainability performance increases transparency about the long-term social and environmental impact of companies and their governance structure (Cormier et al., 2010). Moreover, Lai et al. (2016) and Melloni et al. (2017) both studied have recognized conciseness, completeness, and balance of the information of integrated report. And, 2) altering internal management practices by motivating managers and improving their engagement with key stakeholders (Ioannou & Serafeim, 2012). Cui et al. (2012) documented empirical evidence that CSR can reduce asymmetric information problem. Earlier research of Kilic & Kuzey, 2016; Loh et al., 2017; Hossain et al., 2005 recognized contribution of voluntary disclosures in managing information asymmetry resulting in reduction of agency costs and avoidance of pressure from external stakeholders. Moreover, disclosure of CSR activities can also directly improve managerial practices by motivating managers to focus on sustainable value creation (Shamsuddini & Golbaghi, 2017). Thus, SR diminishes the possibility of agency costs in the form of short-term opportunistic behavior. Study of Scholtens and Kang (2013) found that managers' intention to manage earnings reduces due to additional disclosure of CSR, may mitigate agency problem between managers and shareholders.

Opposite findings also exist in prior studies. Grougiou et al. (2014) documented that U.S commercial banks that involve in earning manipulation, also invest heavily in CSR. Another study in the context of BD by Muttakin et al. (2015) concluded that CSR is used for hiding manager's opportunistic behavior to stakeholders. Hence, the study implies the following hypothesis on the basis of discussion:

H₁: Sustainability disclosures have significant association with agency cost.

3. Methodology

3.1 Sample Selection and Source Documents

Thirty listed commercial banks in Dhaka Stock exchange (DSE) are covered for the study (Appendix table 1). The study considers all the listed banks up to 2008. Among them one is state owned and 29 are private commercial banks. Primary samples comprise 360 bank years from 2008-2019. Data for analysis was collected from multiple sources. Audited financial statements are the basis for obtaining banks

accounting information such as assets and liabilities. Soft and hard copies of annual report of listed commercial banks are collected from DSE library. The market value of stock price has also been collected from same source. The study collected corporate governance and ownership data from the notes of financial statements, the corporate governance compliance report and website of the sample banks. All the data collected is cross-checked from the website of DSE. Sustainability disclosures were collected from CSR disclosures, directors' report, chairman's statements and the notes to the financial statement contained in the annual report. The study has reviewed Bangladesh Bank reports relating to CSR, green banking and sustainable financing disclosures. All the sample banks completed sustainability related disclosures, financial data, and stock market data required for the study. The study did not encounter any situation relating to missing data.

3.2 Variables

3.2.1 Measures of Dependent Variable - Agency Cost

As agency conflict has diversified in nature, some common ratios are used as proxy. Chih et al. (2008) and Muttakin et al. (2015) described that nature of relationship between CSR and earning management (agency problem) depends on which proxies are used. Prior researches used asset utilization ratio (AUR), expense ratio (ER) and cash flow interaction to measure management efficiency in using organizational resources and effectiveness in making investment decisions. But due to difference in financial structure and disclosure items in banking industry, literatures on these context developed slightly modified proxy of agency cost. Marcado-Mendez and Willey (1995); Achary et al. (2014); Siddiqui and Shoaib (2020) focused on different measures of proxies like operating expenses to interest income and operating expenses to total loan; earning volatility, bank size, return on asset (ROA) and Tobin's Q in their studies on agency cost in banking sector. Rashid (2015) claimed accounting profit can be manipulated because accounting figures are prepared by management and managers may select accounting methods that disclose enhanced performance (Rashid, 2015). Wiwattanakantang (2001) and Rashid (2015), argued all agency cost could not be reflected in accounting performance measures such as asset size, return on asset. Hence, the study used three proxies of agency cost that are slightly modified due to different disclosure items in annual reports of banks.

3.2.1.1 Asset Utilization Ratio(AUR)/Asset Turnover Ratio

This ratio used as a proxy for the loss in revenues attributable to inefficient asset utilization (Ang et al., 2000). Thus it measures the ability of management to employ asset efficiently. It is calculated as the ratio of annual revenue (interest Income) to total asset. While a higher level of asset turnover ratio indicates efficient asset management practices and commitment to shareholder value creation, firms with higher AUR lead to lower agency Cost (Singh & Davidson III, 2003). So expected sign of agency cost in this proxy will be negative, as there is inverse relation between AUR and agency cost. As an indication of a reduction in agency cost, it is expected that a positive relationship between sustainability reporting and the agency cost measured by AUR. In case of increase of agency cost the sign will be reversed.

3.2.1.2 Expense Ratios (ER) [Operating Expenses to Interest Income Ratio (OER) and Operating Expenses to Total Loan Ratio (ELR)]

It is known as direct proxy for agency cost (Ang et al., 2000). It is the ratio of operating expenses to total annual sales (interest income). It indicates how effectively the firm's management controls operating expenses and it tends to capture the impact of agency cost. While a higher expense ratio indicates management in efficiency to control expense, firm with higher ER leads to higher agency cost. So, expected sign of agency cost in this ratio is positive. To test the existence of agency cost, slightly different ratios was used for financial organization, because of different financial structure e.g. balance sheet and income statement items are different from other organizations. Achary et al. (2014) applied operating expense to interest income ratio and operating expenses to total loan ratio, modified from expense ratio suggested by (Ang et al., 2000; Singh & Davidson III, 2003). As an indication of a reduction in agency cost, it is expected that a negative relationship between sustainability reporting and agency cost is measured by OER and ELR. In case of increase of agency cost the sign will be reversed.

3.2.2 Measures of Independent Variable – Sustainability Reporting

As boundary sustainability reporting is vast, changing and voluntary, it is difficult for the firms to agree upon on same practices and disclosures. So the study has employed proxy of corporate sustainability reporting, namely; sustainability disclosure index (SDI) by developing index by assigning unweighted score in disclosure of different sustainability aspects (Appendix table 2).

In unweighted index method – equal score is assigned for complying with related issues included in checklist, as every performance in the index is considered equally important (Bose et al. 2021). The study employs content analysis technique to measure sustainability disclosure practices from the listed commercial banks' annual report, this procedure is followed by Khan et al., 2012; Bose et al., 2017; Bose et al., 2020. A firm awarded 1 if one item of sustainability was reported in annual report or in separate report and score 0 if it was not reported. The total sustainability disclosure score was then calculated by adding the score of all individual dimensions. Ultimate index score was calculated as a ratio of total disclosure score achieved to maximum possible performance disclosure for the firm. A higher score index indicates higher level of disclosures. The study include 28 items from four dimension those are appropriate for banking industry. Cronbach's Alpha score 0.90085 indicates that the items of index are consistent and reliable to measure sustainability disclosures.

The index formula can be expressed in the following equation-

$$SDI \text{ index} = \sum_{t=1}^{n_j} X_{ij} / n_j$$

Where, SDI = Sustainability Disclosure Index for i^{th} firm

n_j = Number of items expected for i^{th} firm, where $n \leq 28$

X_{ij} = if j^{th} items are disclosed for firm I, otherwise 0

3.3 Model Specifications

The study develops the three regression models using three proxies of agency cost to test the relation of agency cost with sustainability reporting. All the models includes

some control variables, i.e; managerial ownership, institutional ownership, board independence, dividend yield, firm growth, risk, firm size, age and audit quality in support with previous literatures. All models include dummy variables for year to capture the fixed effect of time invariant variables. The models relate the outcome variables (dependent) to the predictors (independent variables) and the control variables with a provision for the statistical disturbance terms.

$$AUR_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 SDI_{it} + \beta_2 DOWN_{it} + \beta_3 IOWN_{it} + \beta_4 INDOWN_{it} + \beta_5 BDIND_{it} + \beta_6 FAGE_{it} + \beta_7 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_8 LEV_{it} + \beta_9 GROWTH_{it} + \beta_{10} RISK_{it} + \beta_{11} AUDQ_{it} + \beta_{12} Year_D_{it} \dots \dots (Model 1)$$

$$OER_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 SDI_{it} + \beta_2 DOWN_{it} + \beta_3 IOWN_{it} + \beta_4 INDOWN_{it} + \beta_5 BDIND_{it} + \beta_6 FAGE_{it} + \beta_7 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_8 LEV_{it} + \beta_9 GROWTH_{it} + \beta_{10} RISK_{it} + \beta_{11} AUDQ_{it} + \beta_{12} Year_D_{it} \dots \dots (Model 2)$$

$$ELR_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 SDI_{it} + \beta_2 DOWN_{it} + \beta_3 IOWN_{it} + \beta_4 INDOWN_{it} + \beta_5 BDIND_{it} + \beta_6 FAGE_{it} + \beta_7 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_8 LEV_{it} + \beta_9 GROWTH_{it} + \beta_{10} RISK_{it} + \beta_{11} AUDQ_{it} + \beta_{12} Year_D_{it} \dots \dots (Model 3)$$

3.4. Definition of Variables

Table 1: Definition of Variables

Variables	Proxy	Measures	Acronym
Dependent variable Agency cost	Asset utilization Ratio	Ratio of total interest income to total asset	AUR
	Operating expenses to interest income ratio	Ratio of operating expense to total income	OER
	Operating expenses to total loan ratio	Ratio of total expense to total loan disburse	ELR
Independent variable Sustainability Reporting	Sustainability disclosure index	Developing index by assigning unweighted score in disclosure of different sustainability aspects.	SDI
Control variables	managerial ownership	Percentage of share owned by board of directors	BOWN
	Institutional ownership	Percentage of share owned by institutional owners	IOWN
	Individual ownership	Percentage of share owned by individual	INDOWN
	Board independence	Ratio of non-executive directors to the total directors	BIND
	Firm age	Number of year firm has been established	FAGE
	Firm Size	Natural logarithm of total asset	FSIZE

	Leverage	Ratio of total debt to total asset.	LEV
	Asset Growth	Percentage in change in total asset.	GROWTH
	Risk	Natural logarithm of Standard deviation of stock return over years.	RISK
	Audit quality	Dummy variable 1 for firm Audited by BIG4 otherwise 0.	AUDQ
	Year		Year_D

4. Data Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics of the variables are presented in table 2. The table presents mean, median, standard deviation, observations in first and third quartile. The statistics revealed that average (mean) of agency cost measured by AUR, ELR, OER are 9.10%; 3.50% and 31.90% respectively. These findings are consistent with lower AUR with higher OER. The means of sustainable reporting (SDI), is 0.564. The average of managerial ownership is 24.20% for banking companies which much lower than findings of Rashid (2016) for manufacturing companies in Bangladesh. But in case of external owners, the statistics showed average 21.70% share of banking companies owned by institutional investors and average 39.60% share owned by individuals, which is higher than findings of Rashid (2016) for manufacturing companies in Bangladesh. In case of the corporate governance variables, average of independent directors is 14.20 and average 40% firms maintain audit quality with Big 4 audit firm. Director ownership, intuitional shareholding, board independence and audit quality is much better in banking sector compared to non-financial companies based on the findings of Muttakin et al. (2016).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variables	Mean	Median	S.D.	1 st Quartile	2 nd Quartile
AUR	0.091	0.077	0.087	0.067	0.091
ELR	0.035	0.031	0.024	0.024	0.042
OER	0.319	0.276	0.171	0.218	0.376
SDI	0.564	0.571	0.089	0.457	0.754
BOWN	0.242	0.272	0.154	0.109	0.358
IOWN	0.217	0.190	0.142	0.124	0.252
INDOWN	0.396	0.388	0.161	0.275	0.511
BIND	0.142	0.133	0.127	0.067	0.182
FAGE	3.069	2.996	0.448	2.737	3.434
FSIZE	11.886	12.015	0.764	11.408	12.467
LEV	0.922	0.922	0.035	0.905	0.935
GROWTH	0.151	0.145	0.079	0.097	0.201
RISK	0.361	0.326	0.184	0.198	0.471
AUDQ	0.400	0.000	0.491	0.000	1.000

Note: Authors 'own calculation

4.2 Correlation Matrix

Table 3 provides the Pearson's correlation matrix for the key variables in the study. According to table II agency cost proxy by AUR is significantly positively correlated to sustainability disclosure, leverage; board ownership. On the other hand, AUR is significantly negatively correlated to firm size and risk of return. Agency cost proxy by OER has significant negative correlation to level of sustainability disclosure. The highest correlation among the variables is board independence and board ownership is (0.574). This result implies that the analysis is free from multicollinearity.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	AUR	ELR	OER	SDI	BOWN	IOWN	INDOWN	BIND	FAGE	FSIZE	LEV	ASSGROW	RISK	AUDQ
AUR	1													
ELR	0.234 ***	1												
OER	-0.050 2	0.397 ***	1											
SDI	0.101 **	-0.068	-0.324 ***	1										
BOWN	0.077 ***	-0.228 ***	-0.379 ***	0.252 ***	1									
IOWN	0.078	-0.067	-0.153 ***	-0.127 **	-0.094 *	1								
INDOWN	0.049	-0.022	-0.138 ***	-0.085	0.107 **	-0.158 ***	1							
BIND	0.027	-0.085	-0.102 *	0.141 ***	-0.574 ***	0.272 ***	-0.215 ***	1						
FAGE	0.008	-0.213 ***	-0.411 ***	0.098 *	-0.212 ***	0.047	0.024	0.129 **	1					
FSIZE	-0.298 ***	0.151 ***	0.218 ***	0.402 ***	0.267 ***	0.043	-0.056	0.322 ***	0.356 ***	1				
LEV	0.186 ***	-0.160 ***	-0.419 ***	0.291 ***	-0.245 ***	0.079	-0.398 ***	-0.007	0.119 **	-0.345 ***	1			
GROWTH	0.047	-0.169 ***	-0.356 ***	0.088 *	-0.032	-0.146 ***	0.084	-0.123 ***	-0.332 ***	-0.185 ***	-0.232 ***	1		
RISK	-0.179 ***	0.047	0.198 ***	-0.137 **	0.079	0.037	-0.027	0.105 **	0.233 ***	0.256 ***	0.243 ***	-0.505 **	1	
AUDQ	0.041	-0.034	-0.043	0.029	-0.034	0.108 **	0.025	0.066 2	-0.119 **	0.027	-0.117 ***	0.027	-0.143 ***	1

Note: Authors' Own calculation. All the tests are two-tailed tests. ***, ** and * represent significance level at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

4.3. Multivariate Analysis

It is compulsory to comply with the assumptions of multiple regression analysis, before run the models. The study performs necessary test to check data normality. Jarque-Bera normality test for normality (joint chi-square =9.54; p= 0.022) ensures that data is normally distributed. The variance Inflation factor (VIF) for all the variables are less than 3 (appendix Table 3).The means of VIF is very small for all three models. Gujrati (2003), suggested that VIF of more than 10, indicate multicollinearity problem. The study used ‘STATA 16’ statistical package primarily to run the pooled OLS in examining the association between agency cost and explanatory variables. Despite selecting control variables based on their theoretical association and prior empirical evidence, the study acknowledges potential unobserved heterogeneity due to omitted variables. The analysis employ robust standard errors clustered using both bank and year to control heteroscedasticity and serial correlation issues in the models. All regression analysis includes year fixed effect. These methods are consistent with Bose et al. (2021, 2018)

4.3. Result of Regression Analysis

Table 4: OLS regression of Agency cost (AUR), (OER) and (ELR) with sustainability reporting

Variables	Model (1)		Model (2)		Model (3)	
	Coef.	t-value	Coef.	t-value	Coef.	t-value
Intercept	0.284	0.558	1.003***	2.963	0.034	0.930
SDI	0.050**	2.356	-0.041**	-2.212	-0.003**	-2.182
BOWN	0.067*	1.653	-0.149***	-3.371	-0.149***	-2.832
IOWN	0.014	0.221	-0.028	-1.537	-0.027**	-2.223
INDOWN	0.046	0.324	-0.079*	-1.904	-0.003	-0.900
BIND	0.109**	2.160	-0.021***	-8.845	-0.021*	-1.913
FAGE	0.032**	2.111	-0.163***	-9.983	-0.014***	-9.971
FSIZE	-0.067**	-2.152	0.084***	5.928	0.005	0.795
LEV	0.550	1.124	-0.417*	-1.701	-0.033	-0.701
GROWTH	0.026	0.372	-0.294***	-3.732	-0.071***	-3.112
RISK	-0.099**	-2.032	0.082*	1.761	0.031***	2.693
AUDQ	0.020**	2.263	-0.013	-0.963	-0.003	-0.940
Year_D	Included		Included		Included	
Adjusted R ²	0.346		0.656		0.378	
F-test	5.195***		25.428***		8.848***	
Obsevation	360		360		360	

*Note: Authors' own calculation. All the tests are two-tailed tests. ***, ** and * represent significance level at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.*

Table 4 reveals the coefficients of SDI (coef. = 0.05, -0.041, -0.003) are significant at the level of 5% in all the three models (1), (2) and (3), respectively. Thus across all three models, the results consistently shows that sustainability reporting reduce

agency cost proxy by AUR, OER and ELR, thus supporting H_1 . Adjusted R^2 of 34.6%, 65.6% and 37.8% and F-test (5.195,25.428,8.848) in models (1), (2) and (3), respectively implies that model is fit enough to explain the relationship among variables. In sum, the analysis provides strong evidence that sustainability reporting can reduce agency problem in Bangladesh.

4.4 Interpretations of Regression Results

The regression coefficient of the relationship between sustainable reporting and agency cost are presented in table 4. As AUR has inverse relation with agency cost, positive relations with AUR indicate reduction of agency cost. On the other hand, OER and ELR have positive relation with agency cost, negative relation with OER and ELR, indicate reduction of agency cost and vice versa. From the regression results, sustainable reporting has positive direction with AUR and negative direction with OER and ELR, measure of agency cost. This finding has strong and consistence proof that sustainability reporting has significant explanatory power in reducing/minimizing agency cost under all measures of agency cost. From CG variables coefficient of board ownership has positive association with AUR and negative association with OER and ELR, measure of agency cost. The output implies managerial ownership has the strong explanatory power to reduce agency cost. Coefficient of board independence also provide same evidence, implies independent directors contribution in disclosure, thus reduction in agency problem. Institutional investors has negative relation with ELR in model (3), indicate institutional shareholding reduce agency problem when agency cost is proxy by ELR. The coefficients of bank age in three different models indicate older firm may subject to lower agency cost, consistent with Rashid (2016). Bank size has influence in increasing agency cost under AUR and OER. Significant negative coefficient of leverage in model (2) indicates that, firm with debt financing may lead to reduced agency cost because external obligation of payment of interest and monitoring by external parties. Findings also suggest that firm with higher growth opportunities are in less exposure of agency problem under OER and ELR. Audit by Big4 is also act as external monitoring mechanism to reduce agency problem, under AUR. Firm risk of return has significant explanatory power in determining agency cost under all three measures of agency cost, which is consistent with Rashid (2016).

4.5. Check for Robustness

The findings of the study are robust; as the analysis employed a balanced panel, and free from unobserved heterogeneity. Earlier studies argued that relationship between ownership structure and agency cost suffers from spurious effect because of industry specific characteristics (Rashid, 2016; Short and Keasey, 1999). The study covers single industry (only commercial banks), thus, the results are free from the spurious effect (causal relationship) of ownership structure and agency cost.

4.5.1. Additional Test for Endogeneity

The relation between agency cost and sustainability reporting may be a case of endogeneity issue as both are simultaneously determined. The studies identify heteroscedasticity issue in primary OLS regression by conducting Breusch-Pagan /

Cook-Weisberg test (Appendix table 4) and Wooldridge test for autocorrelation (Appendix table 5). Moreover, Durbin and Wu-Hausman (DWH) test found *SDI* has endogeneity problems in measures of agency cost (Appendix table 6). Generalized method of moment (GMM) is more efficient method to deal with heteroscedasticity, auto correlation and endogeneity together (Alhazaimeh et al., 2014). The study employ GMM to overcome endogeneity issues and introduce lag of dependent variable (agency cost) as independent variables. The regression results under GMM method are presented in table 5.

Table 5: GMM for Agency Cost and Sustainability Reporting

Variables	Model (1)		Model (2)		Model (3)	
	Coef.	t-value	Coef.	t-value	Coef.	t-value
Intercept	0.104	0.154	0.163	0.384	0.268	0.883
lag_AUR	0.139**	2.512				
lag_ER			0.148***	2.576		
Lag_OE					0.286***	2.780
SDI	0.444**	2.156	-0.074	-0.658	-0.387***	-2.870
BOWN	0.071**	2.046	-0.004	-0.206	-0.028	-0.510
IOWN	0.029	0.747	-0.017	-1.099	-0.024	-0.399
INDOWN	0.027	0.795	-0.002	-0.111	-0.049	-1.175
BIND	0.624***	3.534	-0.096**	-2.047	-1.037***	-3.213
FAGE	0.027	1.486	-0.014**	-2.359	-0.166***	-7.742
FSIZE	-0.099***	-4.762	0.004	0.869	0.059***	3.249
LEV	0.642**	2.470	-0.017	-0.228	-0.069	-0.317
ASSGROW	0.027	0.439	-0.044**	-2.153	-0.027	-0.380
RISK	-0.149***	-4.146	0.034***	3.073	0.042	0.825
AUDQ	0.021***	2.582	-0.001	-0.451	-0.009	-0.829
<i>AR(1)</i>	-2.06 (P = 0.039)		-2.18(P= 0.035)		-2.66(P= 0.029)	
<i>AR(2)</i>	-0.36 (P = 0.718)		0.76 (P= 0.445)		-0.54 (P= 0.592)	
<i>Sargen test</i>	6.05(P = 0.870)		11.59(P = 0.479)		17.94(P = 0.118)	
<i>Hansen test</i>	17.01(P = 0.199)		11.70(P = 0.470)		18.40(P = 0.189)	
<i>Group</i>	30		30		30	
<i>instrument</i>	28		26		29	

Note: Authors' own calculation. All the tests are two-tailed tests. ***, ** and * represent significance level at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

4.6. Discussion Regressions Findings

The study explores the relationship between sustainability reporting and agency cost among listed commercial banks of Bangladesh. Primary analysis tabulated significant positive association of extent and quality of sustainability disclosures with AUR, measure of agency cost model (1), which means, sustainability reporting reduces agency cost if it is measured as the ability of management to employ asset efficiently. The results imply that comprehensive disclosures signal lower agency conflict as claimed by Sheu et al. (2010). Sustainability reporting is a positive approach towards investors by the firms to maintain trust and good relation (Caesaria & Basuki, 2017).

In model (2), the study documented negative and significant relation between sustainability reporting and agency cost, measured by effectiveness of bank's management to control operating cost (OER). This findings are consistent with Eccles et al. (2001) that responsibility reporting provides critical information on key value drives as human capital, corporate governance, risk management and capacity to innovate, thus, to inform investors about efficiency and market competitiveness. Accordingly, it reduces information asymmetry and chance of managers' opportunistic behavior. In model (3) the study found negative and significant relation between sustainability reporting and agency cost, measured by effectiveness of bank's management to control operating cost in line with general operation (ELR). The findings are consistent with the argument of Cormier et al. (2005) that voluntary disclosures of firms' environmental and social aspect are a mean to reduce agency cost. The study documented the influence of firm specific characteristics - age, size, risk, leverage and corporate governance variable audit quality, institutional ownership on agency cost that were proved by previous literatures. In additional analysis to deal with endogeneity, our findings are robust, due to consistency with OLS estimates

5. Conclusions

It was mentioned earlier, that the aim of the study is to evaluate the impact of sustainability reporting on agency cost in commercial banks of Bangladesh. To do this, a sample of 30 listed commercial banks in DSE is investigated. Consistent with agency and stakeholder theory; socially responsible firms disclose information to confirm stakeholders about their actions. In hypothesis, the study assumed significant association between sustainability reporting and agency cost. This study has employed three measures of agency cost and three measures of sustainability reporting, to test the hypothesis through OLS regression. The result has showed significant impacts of sustainability reporting on agency cost, across all measures. It implies that banks with higher level of disclosures lead to lower agency cost. Based on the findings, the study considers sustainability reporting as strong mechanism for controlling agency cost. This may be because sustainability reporting reduces information gap, likelihood of opportunistic behavior of internal owners or managers, hence, reduce agency problem. In more specifically, sustainability reporting can be an influential factor for better utilization of bank resources and increase effectiveness of bank's management to control operating cost.

This study has recognized some limitations in conclusion. First, accounting data is collected from annual reports. On the word of Rashid (2016),

....in developing countries, due to poor accounting standard and weak legal and institutional characteristics, annual reports do not truly represent the affairs and performance of firms. (p. 619).

Secondly, on the other hand, motive for agency cost in banking companies is not clearly explained. Third, effect of ownership structure may need to be analyzed more carefully. Forth, index of sustainability reporting involving some subjectivity and findings should be interpreted carefully, because, findings may be different because of different proxies. Finally, the study has covered only one sector; the result might be different when many sectors and models will be examined.

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Appendices

Appendix Table 1: List of listed commercial Banks

<i>SL. No.</i>	<i>Name of Banks</i>	<i>Year of listing</i>
1	Pubali Bank Limited	1984
2	Rupali Bank Limited	1996
3	IFIC Bank Limited	1997
4	AB Bank Limited	1995
5	Uttara bank Limited	2004
6	United Commercial Bank Limited	1986
7	Islami Bank Bangladesh Limited	1996
8	The City Bank Limited	1995
9	National Credit and Commerce Bank Limited	2000
10	ICB Islamic Bank Limited	1990
11	Eastern Bank Limited	1998
12	National Bank Limited	1995
13	Al-ArafahIslami Bank Limited	1998
14	Dhaka Bank Limited	2000
15	Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	2001
16	Prime Bank Limited	2000
17	Social Islami Bank Limited	2005
18	Southeast Bank Limited	2000
19	Bank Asia Limited	2004
20	EXIM Bank of Bangladesh Limited	2004
21	First Security Islami Bank Limited	2008
22	Mercantile Bank Limited	2004
23	Mutual Trust Bank Limited	2003
24	One Bank Limited	2004
25	Premier Bank Limited	2007
26	Standard Bank Limited	2003
27	Trust Bank Limited	2007
28	BRAC Bank Limited	2007
29	Jamuna Bank Limited	2006
30	Shahjalal Islami Bank Limited	2007

Appendix Table 2: List of disclosure items considered in the preparation of index

Panel: A	Disclosure Item Index	Environmental disclosures	1 (for disclosure)	0 (non- disclosure)
1	SR_ENV_1	Provide separate green banking reports in annual report.		
2	SR_ENV_2	Corporate environmental policies		
3	SR_ENV_3	Bank's initiatives and engagement in building networks on environmental issues		
4	SR_ENV_4	Adoption of policies and technologies for deducing wastage of water and gas in internal operation		
5	SR_ENV_5	Efficient use of energy through adoption of energy saving bulbs, solar energy		
6	SR_ENV_6	Financing eco-friendly projects		
7	SR_ENV_7	Initiative to reduce wastage of paper through encouraging internal communication by email ,using double sided printing and recycling paper		
8	SR_ENV_8	Programs harmonious with environment such as undertaking beautification program, tree plantation.		
9	SR_ENV_9	Initiative to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (online banking, ATMs, mobile banking)/launching new green product/green marketing.		
10	SR_ENV_10	Information regarding climate change and establishment of climate change fund		
11	SR_ENV_11	Disclosure regarding actual amount spent on different green banking activities		

12	SR_ENV_12	Information on whether the bank has been awarded either for its environment friendly activities or its contributions to environmental improvements and for excellence in environmental reporting practices		
13	SR_ENV_13	Internal training regarding green banking such as education program for employee.		
	Panel B	Corporate social responsibility		
		Community involvement		
1	SR_COM_1	contribution through charitable donation & subscription (free medical service, rehabilitating the disables, orphanage, financial assistance to poor women)		
2	SR_COM_2	banks involvement in sponsorship (sports, cultural program, and religious functions)		
3	SR_COM_3	banks involvement in community program (hospitals for health care, patronizing general and technical education, providing study loan, social awareness program)		
4	SR_COM_4	Contribution to , aiding victims of natural disasters		
5	SR_COM_5	Cash donation program		
6	SR_COM_6	Scholarship to the poor meritorious students		
		Employee information		
1	SR_EMP_1	Employee profile		
2	SR_EMP_2	disclose employee compensation, welfare & donation		

3	SR_EMP_3	Provide information regarding employee education and qualifications.		
4	SR_EMP_4	Information regarding employee training & development		
5	SR_EMP_5	Healthcare facilities for the employees		
6	SR_EMP_6	Employee remuneration and profit sharing		
		Product responsibility disclosure		
1	SR_PRO_1	Different type of product and services		
2	SR_PRO_2	Research and development for product and services		
3	SR_PRO_3	Statement of customer services and facilities		

Appendix Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

<i>Independent and control variables</i>	<i>VIF</i>
SDI	2.34
BOWN	1.06
IOWN	1.03
INDOWN	1.28
BIND	1.28
FAGE	1.56
FSIZE	2.64
LEV	2.68
GROWTH	1.16
RISK	1.14
AUDQ	1.13
Mean VIF	1.57

Appendix Table 4: Test for heteroscedasticity

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroscedasticity Test: Constant variance	
Chi-square	8.37
Prob.	0.0038
Remark	Heteroscedasticity

Appendix Table 5: Test for autocorrelation

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation Test: no first order autocorrelation	
Chi-square	9.23
Prob.	0.0034
Remark	Auto correlation

Appendix Table 6: Test for Endogeneity of sustainability disclosures in three measures of Agency cost

	AUR		OER		ELR	
<i>Variab les</i>	Durbin	Wu- Hausman	Durbin	Wu- Hausman	Durbin	Wu- Hausman
<i>SDI</i>	chi ² =11.14 42 (p = 0.0004)	F- test=21.09 74 (p = 0.000)	chi ² =19.9 413 (p = 0.0000)	F-test= 20.252 (p = 0.0000)	chi ² =15.4 432 (p = 0.0001)	F- test=15.5 60 (p = 0.0001)
Remark	Endogeneity					